

Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C)

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ABSTRACT

Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children, a hyperinflammatory syndrome associated with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2), is a rare but severe complication in children. There is a paucity of knowledge regarding the management of Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C). This review aims to summate the key clinical presentations and management of MIS-C as per current evidence-based guidelines from the national and international bodies.

INTRODUCTION

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2), the causative agent of the covid-19 pandemic has affected millions of lives worldwide [1]. Children are less commonly affected and mostly remain asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic. Among the symptomatic children, 10% - 20% may need hospitalization and among the hospitalized children, intensive care is needed in 1% to 3% of the children with severe illness [2]. In SARS-CoV2 exposed children, a new type of disease entity was reported in April 2020, a clinical syndrome resembling Kawasaki Disease (KD) and toxic shock syndrome which was later termed as Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) [3]. Another name for MIS-C is Pediatric inflammatory multisystem syndrome temporally associated with SARS-CoV-2 (PIMS-TS) [4]. The estimated incidence of MIS-C is 2/100,000 children which is relatively rare but carries high morbidity and mortality [5].

CASE DEFINITION FOR MULTISYSTEM INFLAMMATORY SYNDROME IN CHILDREN (MIS-C):

World Health Organization (WHO) [6], Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [7], and Royal College of Pediatrics and Child Health (RCPCH) [8] have given the following case definitions for Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) as summarized in [TABLE 1].

TABLE 1: MIS-C CASE DEFINITION* [3]

Criteria	WHO	CDC	RCPCH
Age	0–19 years	<21 years	All children (age not defined)
Fever	Fever for ≥3 days	Temperature ≥38.0°C for ≥24 hours or subjective fever for ≥24 hours	Persistent fever (≥38.5°C)
Clinical symptoms	At least two of the following: 1. rash, conjunctivitis, and mucocutaneous inflammation; 2. hypotension or shock; 3. cardiac involvement (presence of myocardial dysfunction, pericarditis, valvulitis, or coronary abnormalities including findings on echocardiogram or elevated levels of troponin/N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide); 4. coagulopathy; 5. acute gastrointestinal symptoms	Both of the following: 1. severe illness (hospitalized); and 2. ≥2 organ systems involved	Both of the following: 1. single or multi-organ dysfunction; and 2. additional features- abdominal pain, confusion, conjunctivitis, cough, diarrhea, headache, lymphadenopathy, mucous membrane changes, neck swelling, rash, respiratory symptoms, sore throat, swollen hands and feet, syncope, and vomiting.

Inflammation	Elevated inflammation markers, including any of the following: 1. raised ESR; 2. raised CRP; 3. raised procalcitonin	Laboratory evidence of inflammation including, but not limited to, one or more of the following: 1. raised CRP; 2. raised ESR; 3. raised fibrinogen; 4. raised procalcitonin; 5. raised d-dimer; 6. raised ferritin; 7. raised LDH; 8. raised IL-6; 9. neutrophilia; 10. lymphopenia; 11. hypoalbuminemia	All three of the following: 1. neutrophilia; and 2. increased CRP; and 3. lymphopenia
Link to SARS-CoV-2	Evidence of COVID-19 by the following: 1. positive by Polymerase chain reaction (PCR); 2. positive by antigen test; 3. positive by serology; or 4. likely COVID-19 contact	Current or recent findings of the following: 1. positive by Polymerase chain reaction (PCR); 2. positive by serology; 3. positive by antigen test; or 4. COVID-19 exposure within prior 4 weeks	Positive or negative by Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)
Exclusion	No obvious microbial cause	No alternative diagnosis	Other infections

WHO = World Health Organization, CDC = Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), RCPCH = Royal College of Pediatrics and Child Health, CRP = C-reactive protein; ESR = erythrocyte sedimentation rate; LDH = lactate dehydrogenase; IL-6 = interleukin-6; COVID-19 = coronavirus disease 2019

PATHOGENESIS OF MIS-C

Several aspects are unclear and are still evolving, what is relatively more certain is that the terminal point of the pathogenesis is cytokine storm, yet poorly understood the postulated mechanisms include the following:

- The most widely accepted theory is that after a SARS-COV2 infection, there is a formation of antibodies against the virus by the body followed by clearance of the virus from the system. Subsequently, there is an IgG-mediated enhancement of the immune response leading to a hyperimmune response causing a cytokine storm. This in turn causes the characteristic multi-system involvement. This hypothesis is supported by the observation that most patients test negative by RT-PCR for COVID but have a positive antibody test, in addition to the lag of three to six weeks between the peak of COVID infection and the peak of MIS-C cases further compound this hypothesis.
- The second hypothesis predicts that after a COVID-19 infection with a heavy viral load, there is a blockade of the interferon responses as has been seen with other coronaviruses. Subsequently, there is a delayed response to the active infection in the form of an exaggerated cytokines surge causing MIS-C.
- The third hypothesis states that instead of directly leading to a cytokine storm, SARS-COV2 may be acting as an intermediate primer or a costimulatory agent or just providing a portal of entry to an as yet unknown trigger that is causing the immune response and causing MIS-C.

Why this phenomenon is occurring predominantly in children and why certain systems are more commonly affected is not definitively known.

CLINICAL FEATURES

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, the Government of India, and the Indian Academy of Pediatrics have endorsed WHO criteria for the diagnosis of MIS-C. Various studies have reported different clinical features of MIS-C as shown in Table 2 and among them, fever is the most common symptom along with Kawasaki disease-like symptoms, gastrointestinal symptoms with or without shock, or cardiac dysfunction [9, 10, 11].

Types of presentation of MIS-C can be categorized into the following:

1. **Mild MIS-C or Febrile inflammatory syndrome (FIS):** This is the most common presentation of MIS-C. No shock like features and no major organs are involved.
2. **Kawasaki disease-like presentation:** This presents with full-blown Kawasaki disease-like symptoms with cardiac involvement but no shock.
3. **Shock with Multi-organ dysfunction:** Shock is the predominant presenting symptom.

TABLE 2: Clinical features of MIS-C [9, 10, 11]

Clinical features	Percentage
Kawasaki disease like symptoms	
Fever	100%
Oral mucosal change	23%–59%
Conjunctivitis	40%–51%
Rash	42%–58%
Cervical lymphadenopathy	4%–17%
Extremity changes	15%
Gastrointestinal symptoms mimicking viral gastroenteritis or mesenteric lymphadenitis	
Abdominal pain	36%–73.7%
Vomiting	25%–68%
Diarrhoea	27%–55%
Any GI symptoms	88%
Cardiovascular abnormalities	
LV dysfunction	34%–82%
Inotropic support	71%–77%
Hypotension	28%–61%
Tachycardia	82%
Pericardial effusions	59%
Coronary aneurysms	13%–23%
Respiratory symptoms (cough, sputum, tachypnoea)	4.5%–42%
Radiographic changing of lung	14%–41%
Renal	
Acute kidney injury	16.3%
Neurological Symptoms	
Headache	37%
Meningism	31%
Meningitis	18%

MIS-C = Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children, GI = gastrointestinal, LV = left ventricular

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

1. **Kawasaki disease:** In MIS-C, a broader age range with older children (mean age 8-10 years) are affected, gastrointestinal symptoms, neurologic symptoms, myocardial dysfunction, and shock is more common, inflammatory markers are highly elevated, thrombocytopenia, lower absolute lymphocyte count is commonly reported. [3]
2. **Toxic shock syndrome:** Microbiological evidence of Staphylococcus/Streptococcus necessary for diagnosis.
3. **Bacterial Sepsis/ septic shock:** difficult to distinguish in absence of microbiological evidence but features like coronary artery abnormalities are unlikely in sepsis.

4. Dengue and Dengue-related Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis (HLH): especially relevant in tropical settings to rule out dengue infection.

5. Other differential diagnosis: includes appendicitis, Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis (HLH) or Macrophage Activation Syndrome (MAS), Lyme disease, tropical diseases which include: Malaria, Dengue, Enteric fever, Rickettsial illness (scrub typhus), Leptospirosis (if suspected), viral syndrome (CMV, EBV, Adenovirus, Coxsackie, varicella, etc.), bacterial enteritis, lupus, vasculitis [12].

DIAGNOSIS OF MIS-C IN CHILDREN

Diagnostic evaluation for Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) includes taking proper history, clinical examination, and necessary investigations to rule out other possible aetiologies. Approach to diagnosis as shown in Figure 1.

INVESTIGATIONS:

Tier 1 Investigations:

- Complete Blood Count (CBC),
- Complete metabolic panel [includes measurement of sodium, potassium, carbon dioxide, chloride, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), creatinine, glucose, calcium, albumin, total protein, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase, and bilirubin],
- Inflammatory markers [Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR), C-Reactive Protein (CRP)],
- SARS-CoV-2 Serology and/or Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR),
- Blood Culture.

Tier 2 Investigations:

- Cardiac [Electrocardiogram (ECG), Echocardiogram (ECHO), B-type Natriuretic Peptide (BNP), Troponin T];
- Inflammatory markers [Procalcitonin, Ferritin, Prothrombin time (PT), Partial thromboplastin time (PTT), D-dimer, Fibrinogen, Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH), Triglyceride, Cytokine panel];
- Blood Smear;
- Urinalysis;
- SARS-CoV-2 serology.
- Investigate for common tropical infections which include: Malaria, Dengue, Enteric fever, Rickettsial illness (scrub typhus), Leptospirosis (if suspected), etc.

TABLE 3: Laboratory parameters suggestive of MIS-C [12]

Evidence of inflammation		Others
CRP > 5 mg/dL	D-Dimer > 2 mg/L	AKI
ESR > 40 mm/h	Fibrinogen > 400 mg/dL	Hyponatremia (Na < 135 mmol/L)
Ferritin > 500 ng/mL	Albumin < 3 g/dL	High LDH
ANC > 7700/ul	Anemia	High troponin
ALC < 1000/ul	ALT > 40 U/L	BNP > 400 pg/mL
Platelet < 150k/ul	INR > 1.2	Prolonged PT or PTT

MIS-C = Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children; CRP = C-reactive protein; ESR = Erythrocyte sedimentation rate; ANC = Absolute neutrophil count; ALC = Absolute lymphocyte count; ALT = Alanine aminotransferase; INR = International normalized ratio; AKI = Acute kidney injury; Na = Sodium; LDH = Lactate dehydrogenase; BNP = B-type natriuretic peptide; PT = Prothrombin time; PTT = Partial thromboplastin time.

Figure 1: Diagnostic Flowchart of Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) [3, 14]

Chest radiograph in MIS-C: Most of the patients have normal chest radiographs. Abnormal findings can include patchy consolidations, focal consolidation, atelectasis, and pleural effusions.

ECG changes in MIS-C: ECG changes were mostly nonspecific. Some of the changes noted in ECG were:

- Repolarization changes with ST- or T-wave segment abnormalities
- Arrhythmia and
- Heart block

ECHO findings in MIS-C: Reported ECHO findings from MIS-C patients are as follows: [13]

- Depressed LV function
- Dilation and aneurysm of coronary artery
- Mitral regurgitation
- Pericardial effusion

MANAGEMENT

The Primary Goals of management in the MIS-C are to stabilize patients with acute life-threatening manifestations such as shock and to prevent long-term sequelae that may include cardiac abnormalities. Children admitted with MIS-C are divided into three categories i.e., mild MIS-C, Kawasaki disease like presentation, and shock and multi-organ dysfunction. Patients are further managed based on these categories as shown in Figure 2 [14].

Immunomodulatory treatment in MIS-C:

Before initiating immunomodulatory treatment in MIS-C without life-threatening manifestations, the child should undergo diagnostic evaluation for MIS-C as well as other possible infections and non-infection-related conditions and keep under close monitoring. However, in cases of MIS-C with life-threatening manifestations, immunomodulatory treatment should be initiated even before the full diagnostic evaluation is completed. [Figure2]

1. Intravenous Immunoglobulin (IVIG): Intravenous Immunoglobulin is considered first-tier therapy in MIS-C patients who are admitted and/or fulfill Kawasaki Disease criteria.

Dose: High-dose IVIG - typically 2 gm/kg over 12-16 hours, based on ideal body weight. (Maximum dose: 100 gm)

Caution:

- Assess cardiac function and fluid status before IVIG treatment is started in MIS-C patients.
- If the cardiac function is depressed, then close monitoring and diuretics with IVIG are required.
- Give IVIG in divided doses (1 gm/kg daily over 2 days) in patients with cardiac dysfunction.
- Even in patients with refractory MIS-C, a second dose of IVIG is not recommended as it increases the risk of volume overload and hemolytic anemia.

2. Glucocorticoids: Glucocorticoids are used as adjunctive therapy in patients with severe disease or as intensification therapy in patients with refractory disease (Refractory disease is defined as persistent fevers and/or ongoing and significant end-organ involvement).

- In few of the mild MIS-C patients who do not show improvement with supportive treatment or have unexplained tachycardia, ill-looking and elevated B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) levels even if they have not yet developed shock or organ-threatening disease, consider giving low-to-moderate-dose glucocorticoids i.e., Methylprednisolone 1–2 mg/kg/day for 3-5 days as first-line therapy.
- In MIS-C with Kawasaki disease like presentation, IVIG 2 gm/kg over 12 -16 hours (maximum 100 grams) along with low-to-moderate-dose glucocorticoids i.e., Methylprednisolone 1-2 mg/kg/day for 3-5 days should be given as first-line therapy. If IVIG is not available, consider giving high-dose pulse glucocorticoids i.e., Methylprednisolone 10-30 mg/kg I.V. (maximum 1 gram) after taking parental consent. In case of treatment failure (persistent fever or ongoing significant end-organ dysfunction after 48-72 hours of starting treatment or recurrence of fever within 7 days), consider giving high-dose IV pulse glucocorticoids i.e., Methylprednisolone 10-30 mg/kg I.V. (maximum 1 gram) and take expert/pediatric rheumatologist opinion for biologics.
- High-dose, IV pulse glucocorticoids i.e., IV Methylprednisolone 10-30mg/kg/day (maximum 1 gram) for 3-5 days along with IVIG 2 gm/kg over 12-16 hours (maximum 100 grams) is used for the treatment of MIS-C patients with shock and/or organ-threatening disease. IV Methylprednisolone may be decreased to 2 mg/kg/day on day 2, if there is a clinical improvement with resolution of shock with fluids on day 1.
- Another steroid at equivalent dosing to Methylprednisolone may be used.
- After 3–5 days of intravenous methylprednisolone, switch to oral prednisolone (1–2 mg/kg/day).
- Steroids should be tapered over 2-3 weeks with clinical and CRP monitoring.

3. Anakinra: A recombinant human interleukin-1 receptor antagonist, is used as an intensification treatment of MIS-C.

Dose: 2–10 mg/kg/dose (max 100 mg/dose) IV or SC

Indications:

- MIS-C refractory to IVIG and glucocorticoids
- Features of macrophage activation syndrome
- If long-term use of glucocorticoids is contraindicated.

4. Tocilizumab: An IL-6 antagonist, may be used in severe cases which do not respond to IVIg, steroid, and anakinra. The dose is 4–8 mg/kg intravenous single dose. [15]. The American College of Rheumatology Clinical Guidance for MIS-C associated with SARS-CoV-2 and Hyperinflammation, does not recommend Tocilizumab for pediatric patients with COVID-19 as there is a lack of benefit reported [5].

5. Infliximab: A TNF- α blocker chimeric monoclonal antibody, Infliximab single dose (10 mg/kg) may be used as a second-line treatment or as an alternative to prolonged and tapering course of glucocorticoids [16].

Immunomodulatory medications may be tapered over 2-3 weeks or even longer based on the response, serial laboratory testing, and cardiac assessment.

Cardiac monitoring

A close clinical follow-up with cardiology is needed in children with MIS-C.

1. Abnormal B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) and/or troponin T at diagnosis should be followed over time until they normalize.

2. Electrocardiogram (ECG) –

- Every 48 hours in admitted MIS-C patients.
- If conduction abnormalities are present- continuous telemetry in admitted MIS-C patients and Holter monitors during follow-up.

3. Echocardiograms (ECHO) -

- Done at diagnosis and during clinical follow-up visits.
- It is repeated at a minimum of 7-14 days and 4-6 weeks after the initial presentation.
- More frequent echocardiograms are required in patients with left ventricular (LV) dysfunction and/or Coronary artery aneurysms.

4. **Cardiac CT** – If distal Coronary artery aneurysms are suspected that are not well seen on echocardiogram.

Antiplatelet and anticoagulation treatment in MIS-C

1. Low dose aspirin:

- Dose: 3-5 mg/kg/day; maximum 75 mg/day
- Aspirin should be given for: -
- 4-6 weeks in all children (with platelet count $>80,000/\mu\text{L}$), and
- at least 4-6 weeks or longer for those with coronary aneurysms [17].
- It is indicated in patients with MIS-C, having Coronary artery aneurysms with a z-score of 2.5-10.0.
- It is continued until platelet count normalizes and coronary arteries are confirmed to be normal at ≥ 4 weeks after diagnosis.
- It is avoided in patients if there is active bleeding or risk of bleeding, and platelet count $\leq 80,000/\mu\text{L}$.

2. Low molecular weight Heparin (Enoxaparin):

- Dose: 1 mg/kg/dose twice daily s/c in >2 months and 0.75mg/kg/dose twice daily s/c in <2 months, maximum dose 40 mg/dose
- Therapeutic anticoagulation with enoxaparin to maintain factor Xa level between 0.5-1.0 is needed in the following:
- Indefinite treatment in coronary artery aneurysms with absolute coronary diameter ≥ 8 mm or with a z-score \geq of 10.0
- Treatment for ≥ 3 months pending thrombus resolution in documented thrombosis in MIS-C patients
- At least 2 weeks after discharge from the hospital in ongoing moderate to severe left ventricular dysfunction. (LVEF $<30\%$)

3. **Warfarin:** Therapeutic anticoagulation with warfarin can be used those MIS-C patients with coronary artery aneurysms with a z-score \geq of 10.0.

For MIS-C patients, antiplatelet and anticoagulation management should be based on the patient's risk for thrombosis.

SUPPORTIVE MANAGEMENT

1. **Fluid resuscitation:** Give bolus of 10 ml/kg and re-evaluate after each bolus. Maintenance intravenous fluids should be used for euvolemia.

2. **Empiric antibiotics:** Empiric antibiotics should be given in all patients with severe MIS-C, until cultures are negative, for 48 hours. Third-generation cephalosporin like Ceftriaxone (100 mg/kg/day bid) should be started empirically. Add vancomycin and clindamycin if toxic shock syndrome is suspected. Add metronidazole if an anaerobic infection is suspected as in a case of possible appendicitis. Antimicrobials should be stopped once cultures are sterile and sepsis is reasonably excluded.

3. **Management of Shock:** Give crystalloid fluid 10 ml/kg and re-evaluate after each bolus. Always be cautious if cardiac dysfunction is there and beware of signs of volume overload. Give early inotrope support when shock persists during or after fluid resuscitation. Epinephrine is considered as the 1st line treatment while norepinephrine can be added if shock persists despite optimal doses of epinephrine. If signs of poor perfusion & cardiac dysfunction persist despite achieving mean arterial pressure target with fluids and vasopressors, consider an inotrope such as Dobutamine/ milrinone.

4. **Other Supportive management:** Gastritis prophylaxis is needed until the patient is off steroids. Respiratory Support may be needed as per the standard protocol.

DISCHARGE CRITERIA:

MIS-C patients can be discharged if the following criteria are met.

1. Afebrile for 48 hours and taking diet orally.
2. Oxygen is not needed.
3. Inflammatory parameters i.e., CRP, Ferritin, and D-dimer are improving or normal.
4. EKG without arrhythmia.

5. Stable/improved latest ECHO.
6. No growth in Blood cultures for 48 hr, if applicable
7. Follow-up is coordinated.

FOLLOW-UP PLAN

First, follow up in 2–3 days.

Indication for repeating laboratory parameters like CRP, CBC, BNP, Troponin, D-Dimer on follow up are as follows:

- If before discharge the laboratory parameters were not normal.
- If there is any recurrence of fever, rash, and gastrointestinal symptoms during weaning from the steroid.
- Cardiology follow up is needed at
- 2 weeks after discharge with repeat EKG and ECHO, and then
- After 4–6 weeks with Echo, and then
- After 1–3 months with Cardiac MRI
- Consider an ECHO 1 year after MIS-C diagnosis, if cardiac abnormalities were present in the acute phase of illness.
- Cardiac MRI may be considered 2–6 months after MIS-C diagnosis in patients who presented in the acute phase of illness with LV ejection fraction <50% or persistent LV dysfunction.

Discharge medications:

- Low-dose aspirin is to be continued until discontinued by the cardiology unit.
- Steroids should be tapered and stopped over 2–3 weeks with clinical and CRP monitoring.
- Gastritis prophylaxis is to be continued until off steroids.

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